

Homosexuality in the Light of Thomas Aquinas' Thought and the Nigerian Experience: An Ethical Appraisal

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Abstract

This paper is a concise scrutiny of homosexuality in the light of the natural law theory of Thomas Aquinas. His theory is also designated as Thomistic Moral Philosophy. The phenomenon of homosexuality is a problem to many people and its social, psychological, medical, religious and cultural consequences are overwhelming. It is against this backdrop that this study takes a critical evaluation of the problem from the ethical thought of Thomas Aquinas by exposing and also analyzing his arguments against the menace of homosexuality. It is one of the objectives of this research to bring to the fore Aquinas' expounded insights in determining the wrongness of homosexuality. Morally and ethically reasons, Aquinas describes and evaluates homosexuality as unnatural, immoral and unethical phenomenon. Homosexuality, from the ethical thought of Aquinas should be avoided. The present research derives its theme from a Christian ethical perspective. The method of analysis of data employed in this work has a multi-methodological approach: phenomenological, descriptive and evaluative. This work contributes to knowledge as it exposes the problem of homosexuality and its negative influence on the young and the old members of our society.

Keywords: Homosexuality, Natural Law, Evil, Ethics, Society, Thomas Aquinas.

Introduction

The recent research has shown that majority of homosexuals believe that they were born as "gays" or "lesbians". This belief, often, emboldens their comfort zones and relieves them of any moral responsibility. However, there appears no verifiable scientific proof that people by birth, are homosexuals. The majority of the gay people, some argue, are genetically normal persons. They are fully either males or females. Some people, on the other hand, are of the opinion that homosexuality is a learned behavior; others reason that the phenomenon is caused by such factors as a disordered family relationship especially some parents who do not show love to their children/wards, peer influence, fear of opposite sex, demonic possession or oppression, among others. Nonetheless, in addition to these factors, one's own free-will has a lot of role to play in terms of formulating one's homosexual life.

Homosexuality is a moral problem and that is the reason for cutting across the personality and identity of an individual person in the society. Unfortunately, many young people including some Nigerian youths who are involved

in homosexuality do not put all these into consideration. Most of them do not even see anything wrong in what they are doing let alone considering its ethical implications for their total wellbeing. Alongside with this, some Nigerian youths that are involved in homosexuality often raise questions like: if homosexuality is wrong or immoral, to what extent and on what basis. It is against this background that this paper discusses these and other related issues from the ethical thought of Thomas Aquinas.

It is one of the objectives of this research to bring to the fore Aquinas' expounded insights in determining the wrongness of homosexuality. Morally and ethically reasons, Aquinas describes and evaluates homosexuality as unnatural, immoral and unethical phenomenon. Homosexuality, from the ethical thought of Aquinas should be avoided. The present research derives its theme from a Christian ethical perspective. The method of analysis of data employed in this work has a multi-methodological approach: phenomenological, descriptive and evaluative. This work contributes to knowledge as it exposes the problem of homosexuality and its negative influence on the young and the old members of our society.

1. Thomas Aquinas' Moral Philosophy: An Overview

Thomas Aquinas is known as the father of natural law theory and this is because of his discourse on natural law forms an integral part of his moral philosophy. However, it has been observed by modern philosophers that so many people have distorted and falsified the Thomistic moral philosophy because they attempt to explain his thought from his "meta-ethics" and his "theory of virtue". Aquinas defines "law" as "a rule or measure of human acts, whereby a person is induced to act or is restrained from acting". Elsewhere, he also defines "law" as "a dictate of practical reason emanating from a ruler". Aquinas also sees law as "an ordinance of reason directed towards the common good and promulgated by the one who has care of the community" (Omogbe, 1993:185). In a general perspective, a "law" is "a precept that serves as a guide to and measure of human action". Therefore, the goodness or rightness of an act is determined by the conformity of such act to the appropriate law. But to Aquinas, the goodness or rightness of an act is determined by the conformity of such act to reason. Accordingly, he holds that all laws that are promulgated to direct and guide human acts in every society are formed based on reasoning.

A nature enlightens us and offers us the aspiration to do good in order to ensure peaceful coexistence with one another. He believed that reason directs our physical inclinations towards our natural goods. Upon the natural inclinations towards specific modes of behaviour, and upon the ability of reason to discern the right course of conduct, we can establish a body of moral principles and rules to guide man's behaviour. The natural law is embedded in human nature and it is absolute. It applies to all peoples at all times even in societies where they do not believe in the existence of God, people can, through the appeal of reason, recognize their natural obligations (Uduigwomen, 2003:89).

According to Aquinas, "all human actions are governed by a general principle or precept that is foundational to and necessary for all practical reasoning: good is to be done and evil is to be avoided. This principle is not something we can ignore or defy; rather, it is an expression of how practical thought or action proceeds in creatures like human beings. Whenever we deliberate about how we should act, we do so by virtue of a natural inclination to pursue those goods or avoid those evils that contribute to or deter us from our perfection, respectively, as human beings.

Aquinas bases his natural law on God, who is the author of nature. Eternal law is the law by which God governs the whole of creation, directing each creature to its respective end. It is the law implanted in the being of every creature, the law which influences every creature the way it behaves and thus fulfill the purpose of God's creation (Omogbe, 1993:185). Aquinas argued that "God has, in his intellect, an idea by which he governs the world. This idea, in God, for the governance of things is the eternal law" (Thomas Aquinas: ST Lallae, 91, 1).

"The Natural Law, as applied to the case of human beings, requires a greater precision because of the fact that we have reason and free will. It is in our nature to act freely (i.e. to be provident for ourselves and others) by being inclined towards our proper acts and ends. That is, we human beings must exercise our natural reason to discover what is best for us in order to achieve the end to which their nature inclines" (Magee, 2013). The natural law is the law by which God governs all creatures according to its being. Humans as rational beings are not governed by God in the same way as the other non-human creatures, but in a special way through "natural law" which is a rational involvement in the "eternal" law (Omogbe, 1993:185-186). Therefore, humans have to work out their choices by acting according to the dictates of the reason and of it prescribes as suitable for "what is best for our nature".

The interplay of human's rationality with the eternal law of God to form natural law can be evident in Gratsch's opinion:

The natural law is nothing else than the participation of the rational creature in the eternal law of God. The natural law, therefore, is God's eternal law is reflected in the inclination of human nature to its proper activity and goal. Human law is the application of the natural law to particular cases". For example, the natural law prescribes that human life should not be endangered needlessly, and traffic laws supplement the natural law by regulating the speed of automobiles, so that human life is not endangered needlessly (2008:126-127).

Any human being who is reasonable and logical must apprehend anything with which human nature is inclined as good; for example, the preservation of life/dignity of human life, procreation, education of children, "the knowledge of God" and life in society. the natural law prescribes the acts of all virtues in the manner that it enjoins all rational creatures to conduct themselves in accordance with reason, which also is to behave virtuously. The natural law is universal; it is one and the same for all men and women in the universe, for all have the same human nature. Both men and women have that consciousness about the fundamental principles of natural law, such as the need to always "do good and avoid evil". Everyone is conscious of the secondary principles of the natural law, such as those which are found in the Decalogue and other scriptures of religions. It is worthy of note that these secondary precepts are deductions extracted from the fundamental principles of the law of nature.

However, a minority of human beings are ignorant of some of these secondary precepts, because their reason is perverted by bad habits, education, or tradition. Thus, some primitive people did not think of theft as wrong, even though it is contrary to the natural law. Furthermore, even more men and women can be ignorant of the more remote conclusions of the natural law.

There are some salient thoughts which one must have in mind in order to have a good grasp and to have the correct interpretation of Thomistic moral philosophy of natural law theory. They are as follows;

- i. God is understood to be the author of nature. God is good and therefore, anything that comes from Him must be good. Then, since nature comes from God, then, anything natural is good.
- ii. The original connotation of the word "nature" in Thomistic vocabulary is neither "physical" nor "biological" but "ontological". The word "nature" most precisely refers to the essence of a substance, in the case of man, to a substance that is a unity of spirit and body.
- iii. In Thomistic philosophy, "Natural law ethics" and "virtue ethics" are integrally interwoven. This is because "virtues are perfection of man's nature". And if one commits any sin, then he has violated some virtues.
- iv. Right from the time man fell, his corporeal nature and rational nature have been defective which often affect his acts negatively. Thomistic moral philosophy (Natural law moral code) also encompasses various epistemological claims, but such elements are not of great relevance to the purpose of this study.

As earlier noted, Aquinas is of the view that "all human actions are governed by a general principle or precept that is foundational to and necessary for all practical reasoning: good is to be done and evil is to be avoided. This principle is not something we can ignore or defy. Rather, it is an expression of how practical thought and action proceed in creatures such as ourselves". "Whenever we deliberate about how we should act, we do so by virtue of a natural inclination to pursue (or avoid) those goods (or evils) that contribute to (or deter us from) our perfection as human beings. The goods for which we have a natural inclination include life, the procreation and education of offspring, knowledge, and a civil order" (ST Lallae, 94.2). Their contributions toward our reasoning perfection will determine if there are supplementary good – will.

"While we naturally desire goods that facilitate our perfection, excessive passion, unreasonable fear, and self-interest can distort the way we construe those goods" (ST Lallae, 94.6). "For example, sexual pleasure is a natural good. Yet, excessive passion can corrupt our understanding of what sex's role ought to be in our lives and lead us to pursue short term sexual pleasure at the expense of more enduring goods. The thomistic notion of natural law has its roots, then, in a quite basic understanding of the universe as caused and cared for by God, and the basic notion of what a law is. It is a fairly sophisticated notion by which to ground the legitimacy of human law in something more universal than the mere agreement and decree of legislators. Yet, it allows that what the natural law commands or allows is not perfectly obvious when one gets to the proximate level of commanding or forbidding specific acts. If grounds the

notion that there are some things that are wrong, always and everywhere, i.e. “crimes against humanity”, while avoiding the obvious difficulties of claiming that this is determined by any sort of human consensus. Nevertheless, it still sees the interplay of people in social and rational discourse as necessary to determine what in particular the natural law requires” (IEP).

Aquinas argues that the purpose of sexuality is reproduction. Therefore, all sexual activities intended for the purpose of reproduction are in accordance with natural law; non-reproductive sexual activities are contraventions of the law (Ibanga in Ekwealo, 2012:105). Suffice it to say that natural laws are said to be precepts which, through reason, are discovered to be evident in nature. These laws, according to Aquinas are universal and known to all. Natural law holds that man is a natural being; and those actions that are good are those that are in “accord with his nature and with the nature of other things”. “Since man is by nature a rational animal”, those of his actions that are good are those that are rational which are in accordance with his nature (Smith, 2000). In conclusion, any act which impedes the natural purposes which the author of nature (God) has given to things is an act against the author of nature (God) Himself. Therefore, such act is considered wrong. We shall now look at homosexuality and masturbation in the light of Thomistic moral philosophy (Natural law theory).

2. Conceptualizing Aquinas’s Ethical Thought on Homosexuality

The ethical thought of Thomas Aquinas is still resonates with scholarship and practice especially from the Christian perspective. His ideas, particularly in sexual ethics, have shaped the Christian pedagogy. Some of his major discourse on the phenomenon of human sexuality is gleaned from the following works: *Summa Contra Gentiles* (Summa against the Infidels) and *Summa Theologiae* (Summation of Theology). *Summa contra Gentiles* dates from the early part of his teachings in Italy between 1261 AD and 1263 AD. It was intended for the Dominican missionaries who laboured among the moors and ‘pagans’ in Spain and elsewhere (Gratsch, 2008; xiii). In corroboration, Aquinas asserts:

We have said that God exercises care over every person on the basis of what is good for him. Now, it is good for each person to attain his end, whereas it is bad for him to swerve away from his proper end. Now, this should be considered applicable to the parts, just as to the whole being; for instance, each and every of his acts, should attain the proper end. Now, though the male semen is superfluous in regard to the preservation of the individual, it is nevertheless necessary in regard to the propagation of the species. Other superfluous things, are not at all necessary; hence, their emission contributes to man’s good. Now, this is not what is sought in “the case of semen, but, rather to emit it for the purpose of generation, to which purpose the sexual act is directed. But man’s generative process would be frustrated unless it were followed by proper nutrition, because the offspring would not survive if proper nutrition were withheld. Therefore, the emission of semen ought to be so ordered that it will result in both the production of the proper offspring” (SCG III, 22).

Again, Aquinas is of the view that every release of spermatozoa, in the manner that conception does not follow, must be a sin especially if this is done deliberately (SCG III, 22). He further asserts, “... now, I am speaking of a way from which, in itself, generation could not result: such would be any emission of semen apart from the natural union of male and female. For which reason, sins of this type are called contrary to nature” (SCG III, 22). He further argues that “the good which semen is directed towards, is such that to use it for something other than its purpose is in contrary to the good of human life towards which it is directed”. In other words, the semen is meant for fecundity and fecundity is a good of human life, therefore, it would be seriously wrong to use the semen for other things. For in so doing, one would be violating the good of human life of which semen is directed to. God’s intention of creating humans in both sexes (“Adam and Eve”: not “Adam and Steve”, nor “Ada and Eve”) is for the purpose of fruitfulness and multiplication through procreation. In his words, he writes “if God had not intended humans to share in the procreation of new human life, he would not have created humans of two sexes” (Question 92, article 1 of SCG III). Therefore, if humans existing in two sexes are so to bring forth new human life, then the prime good of human sexuality is simply procreation.

More so, Aquinas perceives homosexuality as an act that is contrary to nature and this is evident in his works, *Summa Contra Gentiles* (III, 122) and *Summa Theologiae* (1st part of the 2nd part, question 94, article 3, reply 2). To him, all forms of immorality are antagonistic to nature because they all disrupt the natural order, that is, they do not

go in accordance with the human rationality. In other words, all forms of immorality are unnatural simply because they are not in concord with reason. This is not to deny the fact that some immoral acts still retain some level of naturalness. Let us take the act of fornication as an example. Fornication is immoral simply because it is done outside or before wedlock. Yet, since fornication still stand the chance of fulfilling the highest good of sexual intercourse which is the generation of offspring by a “natural” means which is allowing the penis to introduce semen to the vagina. That means that fornication is an immoral act but not unnatural. But homosexual acts do not achieve anything close to this level of naturalness.

The issue of heterosexuality completes the human person physically, psychologically, medically and naturally. It is also the suitable circumstance of nature in order to allow procreation take place. Thomas Aquinas places a high value on semen and that its part and parcel of his understanding of the reason for the differentiation of the sexes and of the love of God for new human souls. Homosexuality, like masturbation, is immoral and unnatural because it involves wasting the substance (semen) that should be used to bring forth another new life. According to his ethics, all sins that involve misuse of the sexual faculties are considered to be sins of unfaithfulness (i.e. one is using one’s sexual powers outside of the marital relationship or not in accordance with the good of the marital relationship). Aquinas therefore judges homosexual acts of sexual intercourse to be objectively disordered because they are not ordered to the goods that are naturally embedded in sexual intercourse.

In citing some of the instances of the problem, the corruption of the soul, he points at a human custom that takes pleasure in unnatural intercourse, bestiality, or cannibalism. Aquinas speaks of homosexuality emanating through some of the defects that may lead to some moral defects. Consequently, it does not matter whether one is morally blameworthy for getting homosexual condition by oneself or not, or even if the person became homosexual genetically as some people claim; Aquinas would still see it as unnatural or disordered pattern. The phenomenon does not offer any good intrinsically and cannot be channeled towards anything good.

As a theologian, Aquinas judges homosexual acts as “a type of unnatural sexual act termed ‘the unnatural vice’”. This terminology, referring to homosexual acts as unnatural, is in accord with sacred scripture in Paul’s letter to the Roman 1:26-28” (Conte, 2011). “The ‘natural use of the body’ to which Paul refers is that type of sexual act, between a man and a woman, which is inherently capable of procreation. The natural sexual act is inherently ordered toward procreation. But, if a couple is infertile due to injury, illness, or old age; that type of act remains inherently ordered toward the end of procreation, even though the end cannot be achieved”. Therefore, such act remains natural and moral. “Paul condemns homosexual acts, sexual acts between persons of the same gender. Homosexual sexual acts, whether lesbianism or gayism, are disgraceful and morally depraved; this type of sexual act is intrinsically evil and always gravely immoral” (Conte, 2011). Again, in *Summa Theologiae* (11-11, Q54), he writes:

....wherever there occurs a special kind of deformity whereby the venereal act is rendered unbecoming; there is a determinate species of lust. This may occur in two ways: first, through being contrary to right reason, and this is common to all lustful vices; secondly, because, in addition, it is contrary to the natural order of the venereal act as becoming to the human race and this is called “the unnatural vice” ... thirdly, by copulation with an undue sex, male with male, or female with female, as the Apostle states (Romans 1:27) and this is called the vice of sodomy.

Also, in the section of 11-11, Q154, Art.12, a question was raised as to “whether the unnatural vice is the greatest sin among the species of lust?” In the response, Aquinas corroborates and quotes Augustine as having asserted that of all these, namely the sins belonging to lust, that which is against nature is the worst. Taking a cue from Augustine, Aquinas declares as follows:

In every genus, worst of all is the corrupt of the principle on which the rest depend. Was the principles of reason are those things that are according to nature, because reason presupposes things as determined by nature ... therefore, since by the unnatural vices man transgresses that which has been determined by nature with regard to the use of venereal actions, it follows that in this matter this sin is gravest of all”. (ST, 11-11, Q154, Art.12).

Homosexuality is a gravely sexual act; more gravely than fornication, adultery, incest, and prostitution, among others. The only sin that is worse than homosexuality in Aquinas' thought is bestiality: "Gravity of a sin depends more on the abuse of a thing than on the omission of the right use. Wherefore among sins against nature, the lowest place belongs to the sin of uncleanness, which consists in the mere omission of copulation with another. While the most grievous is the sin of bestiality, because, the use of the due species is not observed (11-11, Q154, Art. 12, reply to obj.4).

In Aquinas' thought, "the female body and the male body are designed to operate sexually in union with each other. Homosexual activity defies the innate design of the human body. Studies have proven that such unnatural sexual acts lead to devastating physical, mental and emotional wreckage" (Kukla, 2014). Heterosexuality turns out to be the healthiest relationships in which couples are most happy and children are provided the best opportunities for success. Over the time, humans of every culture, creed and race have recognized the necessity for heterosexual marriages within their communities. In fact, recognizing and desiring such as marriage remains innate to human existence. Again, Aquinas holds that the raising of next generation occurs best in a heterosexual, lifelong marriage. This is the relationship that produces the most children and the children with the most virtue and advantages to make for healthier. Lifestyles that contribute more to the society, therefore, nature inclines all people to preserve and promote such an arrangement. In other words, nature predisposes mankind to make policies which serve the greatest good in the society.

An initial objection raised against Aquinas' natural law theory is the rightness and wrongness of the activities of circus performers and acrobats who always walk with their hands. Now, the questions are: has 'walking with the hands' not thwarted God's natural purpose of the hand? Are hands meant for walking? Does this not violate the natural law? Is this act morally right?. Aquinas' response shows that this objection is not meeting him unaware. He therefore posits that it is not every time we use the body against its natural function that we have perform the wrong act. Consequently, "walking with hands" cannot be seen as a sin simply because, "man's good is not much opposed by such inordinate use". It is not a sin if we use any body part for something else other than its natural function so far as it is beneficial to man. "Walking on the hands" does not aggravate the natural functioning of the whole and God-given role of the whole; therefore, it is not wrong in Thomistic moral philosophy." But homosexuality does frustrate this purpose. Man is designed by God to procreate and homosexuality thwarts that function. That makes it morally wrong" (Stephen Law, 2007).in as much as we humans continue to repudiate truth of our nature and we continue disregarding nature, it will surely bounce back on us. Even if we refuse to sleep as due, nature will make us pay for it somewhere somehow. The unnaturalness of homosexuality remains constant and it has not stopped to be an "unhealthy lifestyle". Homosexuality affects negatively both the individual and the society at large. Though it will take efforts to convince the contemporary society especially the youth to desist from this act, but this difficulty does not mean that it is not possible to achieve.

Homosexuality destroys the natural definition of marriage and God's established norm for sex and marriage through God's creation. God did not bring another man for Adam; instead he brought Eve (a woman. If everyone goes by homosexuality, how do humans sustain the future of humanity? Therefore, homosexuality does one no good. However, this is not to say that the only purpose of human sexuality is procreation. Sex does not need to be procreative or of a procreative kind (that is when procreation is neither intended nor possible) in order for it to be morally valuable. Other than procreation, sex can be a wonderful way of celebrating, enhancing and replenishing intimacy in a married relationship, that is, an expression of affection and solidarity.

3. Discussion: Homosexuality among the Nigerian Youths

The fact that homosexuality is prominent among Nigerian youths of today is of no reasonable doubt. It is difficult to ascertain the period at which homosexuality began among the Nigerian youths. Some have argued that the phenomenon has been in Nigeria right from the time immemorial while some others argued that act is not part of Nigerian custom. One fact that is not disputable is that the agitation by some Nigerians towards the acceptance and recognition of homosexuality in Nigerian legal system is strictly out of the Western influence. Homosexuality has now deeply penetrated the Nigerian nation even though it is against the Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria. The *Newswatch Magazine* (November 21, 2011) entitled: "Sodom Now Here", throws light on the issue of homosexuality as practiced among some Nigerians especially the youths. In its account, the periodical observes:

“Same sex marriage is far more widespread in Nigeria than many people know and the campaign for its legalization is backed by highly placed and wealthy Nigerians in and outside the country”.

In Nigeria, homosexuality and any form of same-sex union is prohibited. The punishment for this unlawful act is 14 years imprisonment for any convicted individual and “capital punishment for men in areas under Sharia law” especially in the northern part of the country. “On January 18, 2007, the Federal Executive Council approved a law – same-sex marriage (prohibition) Act 2006, forbidding homosexual marriages and sent it to the National Assembly for urgent action. The law was said to have been pushed by the former President Olusegun Obasanjo sequel to the demonstrations for same-sex marriage during the international conference on HIV/AIDS (ICASA) in 2005. The bill proposed 5 years imprisonment for anyone who undergoes, performs, witnesses, aids, or abets a same-sex marriage. Though the bill received a little or no opposition in the parliament, yet it was not passed into law nearly 5 years after its arrival. The same-sex marriage ban would make Nigeria the second country in Africa to criminalize such unions after Uganda in 2005” (Dafese, 2015:69).

On the 29th November, 2011, the Nigerian Senate passed the bill and criminalized the same-sex erotic relations, although the bill rekindled anxiety among the homoerotic relations in Nigeria. In the wake of that legislative action, there were arguments and debates concerning homosexuality. In fact, the entire debate revolves around the fundamental question of moral status of homosexuals; it also raises the legal, the religious, the biological and the philosophical issues regarding to what are considered to be normal or abnormal sexual relations within the Nigerian society (Ibanga in Ekwealo, 2013:116).

The Nigerian Senate passed the “anti-same-sex marriage bill” barring any form of homosexual union. The bill prescribes 14 years of imprisonment for anyone found guilty of the act and 10-years imprisonment for anyone found guilty of helping, assisting or supporting the union of people of the same-sex in the country, and also nullifies or disregards any certificate issued by countries where homosexuality is legally allowed. This bill is said to have been underwritten and proposed by “Senator Magnus Abe” (Rivers State). This bill also forbids any setup and activities of gay or lesbian clubs within the shores of the country. Any violation of this attracts a punishment of 10-years imprisonment with no bail. The House of Representatives also joined their senate counterparts to vote in support of the bill. This bill was finally assented to by President Goodluck Jonathan on the 7th of January, 2014. This law is popularly supported by Nigerians and has been widely praised throughout the country especially by the religious leaders. Despite this, the practice has continued to assume the alarming heights, even right under the nose of some of the legislators (Dafese, 2015:84).

The social media is another important facilitator of homosexuality among the Nigerian youths. The *Facebook*, for example, has several groups and pages meant for homosexuals. Examples of such are “Lesbians who Tech (and Friends San Francisco // Holiday Party)”, “sweat for lesbians 25.12.”, “Lesbians who Tech (and friends) South Florida December Happy Hour”, “Lesbians and Gays support this migrants: Open meeting”, among others. Some Nigerian youths might open these pages followed by the urge to apply what has been seen or read in these pages.

3.1. Some Causes of Homosexuality among Nigerian Youths

Over the years, various scholars have conducted thousands of extensive studies in order to arrive at the causes of homosexuality in human society especially among youths. Such studies have been inconclusive. This is because, up till date, there has not been a generally accepted root cause of homosexual acts among youths. A scholar corroborates this view thus:

Despite probably thousands of scientific studies, one conclusion seems clear: there is no clearly identified single cause of homosexuality. A number of competent researchers have investigated whether sexual orientation and homosexual behaviour are the direct result of heredity or other biological influences. Some have concluded that “scientific evidence supports the view that hormonal and neurological variables, operating during gestation, are the main determinants of sexual orientation. Even medical and biological researchers conclude that “post natal socialization” is more likely to influence sexual preference. Stated in less technical terms, there is no solid evidence to support the view that homosexuality has only a physical or biological cause” (Collins, 1988:282).

The causes of homosexuality among Nigerian youths can be traced to four essential factors: a) Wrong friends’ influence or evil association which corrupts good manner, b) lack of control over one’s thoughts and mind especially

after watching pornographic films/images which is rampant in Nigerian society today. Most of Nigerian the youths look for a way to ease themselves after watching pornography turning to any available person even of the same sex, c) to some Nigerian youths, homosexuality becomes part of them as it is a prerequisite to join secret cult. In other words, homosexuality or homosexual act can be one of the initiation rites in some secret cults in Nigerian higher institutions, and, d) since a good number of Nigerian youths are extremely inquisitive; they may gradually become homosexuals by a way of trying or experimenting new things. Some Nigerian youths are homosexuals today as a result of being extremely inquisitive.

Harmer et al (1993), cited in Dafese (2015), found out that brothers of their gay subjects had a 13.5 percent chance of also being gay. Furthermore, male relatives on the “subjects’ mother’s side of the family but not on the father’s side” had a significantly higher rate of homosexuality. This led to the investigators to suspect that “a gene influencing sexual orientation might be located on the X chromosome, the sex chromosome contributed by the mother after studying the DNA on the X chromosomes of 40 pairs of gay brothers, the researchers discovered that 33 of the pairs carried matching genetic information on the end tip of the X chromosome”. But an exact gene has not being identified among the several hundred genes carried within that end tip. LeVay and Harmer (1994) suggest that the way orientation is yet to be known. They therefore concluded that homosexuality is the result of an interaction of biological, psychological and social influences.

Collins (1988:283-285) has outlined 5 causes of homosexuality among youths following psychological development and social learning.

3.1.1. Parent-Child Relationships

Most Nigerian male youths who now have homosexual attraction are brought up in families where the fathers are feeble, futile and inactive with dominant mothers. In a family like this, the mother will always make the male child to be feeble and loyal to her just like her husband. Sooner than enough, the male child will discover that he is not as proficient as other of his male peers especially when it comes to approaching and connecting with females. Thereby, the male child will not be self-confident in his maleness. Such male child will also be confronted with fears over having an intimate relationship with females. A girl-child who is in this type of family perceives her father to be rejecting and unfriendly, therefore she relates better with women or other girls since she has little opportunity to relate to men. While some Nigerian youths became homosexuals as a result of disruptions in parent child relationships; some others do not, and that is why scholars in this regard (ethicists, psychologist, sociologist, etc) seek other causes of homosexuality.

3.1.2. Other Family Relationships

There are some parents who wanted a daughter but they have a son, instead. Some of these parents raise such son to think and act like a girl. A similar situation arises when parents wanted a son but instead have a daughter. In both situations, the child has great confusion over his or her own sexual identity and orientation. There are some mothers who distrust or fear women; therefore, they teach this to their sons. Some mothers also teach the fear of men to their daughters. All these can be factors responsible for homosexual behaviours among Nigerian youths.

Another family situation is when a son is surrounded by too many females (mothers, sisters, aunts) with less or no contact with males, thus he starts acting like females. The same thing is applicable to girl-child surrounded by males, with limited contact with females. Another cause of homosexuality among Nigerian youths from the family is the situation where both parents are unwilling to discuss sex and sex-related issues with their children at home, thereby, exposing their children to the risk of falsehood teachers (peer) outside. Perhaps, there are a lot of causes of homosexuality that are embedded in the family as a place of orientation for any child before coming in contact with other agents of socialization.

3.1.3. Early Life Experiences

It would be too simplistic and erroneous to say that homosexuality among Nigerian youths, comes mainly because early life sexual experiences. Yet, one can conclude that these experiences can have influence on youths’ sexual orientation in one way or the other. Collins (1988:1284) gives a report which suggests that homosexuality can be acquired in three stages; namely: egocentric stage, sociocentric stage and universalistic stage. At stage one(egocentric stage), the child or young adolescent has trouble relating to same-sex peers, feels inadequate and different (perhaps because the young person lacks athletic or other skills that peers possess), and experiences some

erotic arousal with a person of the same sex. Sometimes children feel so inadequate or uncomfortable with their sexual identity and they want to become members of their opposite sex. Most of these children become homosexuals at their youthful age.

At stage two (the sociocentric stage), the individual begins to sense a same-sex orientation, often there are attempts to deny this to oneself and efforts to hide it from others. Many struggle at this stage for their whole lives while, some move to stage three which is called the universalistic stage where they admit their homosexuality to themselves and to others despite the consequences.

3.1.4. Fear

So many Nigerian youths today have become homosexuals as a result of fear of their opposite sex. This fear of opposite sex emanates from lack of frequent contact with opposite sex (especially their age mates), rejection from opposite sex and/or traumatic and embarrassing experiences with people of opposite sex. This fear of the opposite sex is accompanied by fear or awkwardness around members of the same sex. When one cannot freely relate with the opposite sex, relating with people of the same sex becomes the best alternative thereby looming large homosexuality. Some scholars have suggested that homosexuality is more rampant in same-sex schools (Alawa and Ezedike, interv.). In other words, religious groups or same-sex schools (in Nigeria) inadvertently promote homosexuality (Collins, 1988:284) among Nigerian youths.

3.1.5. Willful Choice of Homosexuality

Although this is not a very common cause of homosexuality among Nigerian youths, yet it's possible that some of them have become homosexuals out of deliberate choice. In other words, sexual attraction to the members of the same sex rarely, if ever, comes as a willful and conscious decision among Nigerian youths. Homosexual tendencies are acquired often before one realizes what is taking place. Just as a predominantly heterosexual person is attracted by the opposite sex, so a predominantly homosexual has learned an attraction for the same sex. These attractions are not wrong. What is wrong there is the willful decision to engage in homosexual actions.

No matter how sexual behaviour got started (may be as a result of seduction by another person, as an expression of curiosity, or as an attempt to release tension while one is in the military or confined to jail), it is apparent that anytime one is involved with something pleasurable especially sex with either the same or opposite sex, one finds it more pleasurable the subsequent times. And this is an important issue that has kept most Nigerian youths in homosexuality till day since lasting homosexual patterns tend to be established by recurrent homosexual practices. In other words, one sexual experience can lead to another and as a result, a vicious circle begins. Homosexual acts (including masturbation with homosexual fantasies) increase homosexual tendencies that in turn lead to more homosexual acts.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In Thomistic moral philosophy the word "natural" has an abstract connotation. Everything in existence has "essences" or "natures" which are good. They are created by God and everything that works in accordance with them flourishes. Therefore anything that is seen as natural is good for humans, since they are created for the purpose of serving good to humanity with distinctive and exceptional purposes as designed by God. Clergymen and women, ethicists, and philosophers among others who guide the moral standard of the society should rise to the menace of homosexuality among Nigerian youths which attempt to destroy not only the lives of Nigerian youths but also the socio-ethical structure of Nigerian society today. It becomes very disheartening to learn of high profile clergymen supporting and endorsing gay practices and lesbianism.

The Nigerian government has made success in criminalizing homosexuality as a major way of curbing such act especially among youths in the country. Nevertheless, the Nigerian government should think beyond criminalization policy and endeavor to address the issue of rapid economic down-turn in the country. This will be a measure to dissuade those who go into homosexuality as a result of poverty. The level of poverty in the country has also made some young men to remain single thereby seeing masturbation as a cheaper alternative. The ministry of education should inculcate ethical teachings (especially sexual ethics) into school curriculum right from the secondary school. It has been observed that most social vices in the country today, start from secondary schools and even primary

schools. At the university level, the curriculum for ethics should be broadened and made compulsory for students so that we can inculcate some values into our youths.

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